

Synthesis and characterization of isothiobiurets of *N*-glucosylated compounds and their antimicrobial activities

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Manuscript received 21 January 2011, revised 04 May 2012, accepted 01 August 2012

Abstract : A series of several 1-aryl-5-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -glucopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2-isothiobiurets have been prepared by the interaction of aryl *S*-benzylisothiocarbamides and tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -glucopyranosyl isocyanate. The required aryl *S*-benzylisothiocarbamides was prepared by *S*-benzylation of different thioureas and tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isocyanate was prepared by interaction of tetra-*O*-acetyl- α -D-glucopyranosyl bromide and lead cyanate. The structures of the newly synthesized compounds have been established on the basis of usual chemical transformations and IR, ¹H NMR and Mass spectral studies. All the synthesized compounds have been evaluated for their *in vitro* antibacterial and antifungal activity against different bacteria and fungi by agar diffusion method.

Keywords : *N*-Glucosides, aryl *S*-benzylisothiocarbamides, glucosyl isocyanate, isothiobiurets.

Introduction

The chemistry of thiourea of carbohydrate is extensively elaborated and well documented¹. Many of these derivatives have been found to possess wide applications in industry as carbohydrate based detergent² and in medicine as anticancer agents³ and antifungal agents⁴.

These compounds arouse interest as potential biologically active substances and versatile intermediate for preparing various derivatives. The biological activity of some polyhydroxy compounds have been reported^{5,6}.

Glucopyranosyl isocyanate and isothiocyanate⁷, likewise other glycosyl isocyanates have a significant role in synthetic carbohydrate chemistry. Many compounds have been synthesized by the use of glycosyl isocyanate. For example, galactosyl isocyanide⁸, galactosyl amino derivatives⁹ and other heterocycles¹⁰, but there is no report on the synthesis of isothiobiurets having a β -glucopyranosyl substituent. On the basis of knowledge gained on the work done on *N*-glucosylated isomonothio and dithiobiurets^{11,12}, it was quite interesting to synthesize some new *N*-glucopyranosylated thioamides.

Herein, we report the synthesis of 1-aryl-5-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -glucopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2-isothiobiurets by the interaction of tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -glucopyranosyl isocyanate and aryl *S*-benzylisothiocarbamides. All the products ob-

tained have been crystallized from ethanol-water. IR spectra of the products show characteristic absorption of prominent peaks, ¹H NMR spectra shows characteristic peaks due to N-H, acetyl and glucopyranosyl protons while the Mass spectra shows peak due to acetoglucose unit¹³⁻¹⁵.

Results and discussion

Several 1-aryl-5-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -glucopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2-isothiobiurets (**3a-g**) (Scheme 1) were prepared by the condensation of aryl *S*-benzylisothiocarbamides (**1a-g**) and tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -glucopyranosyl isocyanate (**2**) in benzene for 4 h. The reaction was monitored by TLC. After complete reaction, the solvent was distilled off and the resultant sticky residue was triturated with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) to afford the products (**3a-g**). All the products were crystallized from ethanol-water. Structures of all synthesized products were established on the basis of usual chemical transformations and IR, ¹H NMR and Mass spectral studies.

Antimicrobial activities :

All the compounds have been screened for both antibacterial and antifungal activities using cup plate agar diffusion method by measuring the inhibition zone in mm. The compounds were taken at concentration of 1 μ g/ml using dimethyl sulphoxide as a solvent. Amikacin was used as standard for antibacterial activities and Fluconazole

where, R = (a) phenyl, (b) *o*-Cl-phenyl, (c) *m*-Cl-phenyl, (d) *p*-Cl-phenyl, (e) *o*-tolyl, (f) *m*-tolyl, (g) *p*-tolyl; Ac = -COCH₃, Bz = -CH₂C₆H₅

Scheme 1

Table 1. Physical data of 1-aryl-5-tetra-O-acetyl-β-glucopyranosyl-2-S-benzyl-2-isothiobiurets (3a-g) (Scheme 1)

Sr. no.	Reactant (g)	Product	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	[α] _D ³⁹ (c, CHCl ₃)	R _f (3 : 2, CCl ₄ : EtOAc)
1.	1a (1.21)	3a	100–101	72	122.2° (0.9)	0.93
2.	1b (1.40)	3b	88–90	74.94	-32.5° (0.93)	0.85
3.	1c (1.40)	3c	125–130	82.21	-84.2° (0.95)	0.80
4.	1d (1.40)	3d	115–120	80.50	85.1° (0.94)	0.79
5.	1e (1.28)	3e	110	75.96	52.5° (0.96)	0.90
6.	1f (1.28)	3f	130–135	78.50	-33.3° (0.9)	0.87
7.	1g (1.28)	3g	138	71.60	43.0° (0.93)	0.85

as a standard for antifungal activities. The compounds were screened against various pathogenic bacteria such as *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium*. Among synthesized compounds **3a**, **3b** and

3c show strong activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and remaining compounds show good and moderate activity against *Proteus vulgaris*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Penicillium*. Results are tabulated in Table 2.

Table 2. Antimicrobial activities of synthesized compounds

Compd.	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>Penicillium</i>
3a	20	11	18	22	10	12
3b	21	13	15	20	9	14
3c	12	9	15	17	14	16
3d	15	12	13	14	11	17
3e	23	0	17	20	8	9
3f	14	9	10	11	8	0
3g	10	9	12	13	10	0
Amikacin	17	17	17	17	-	-
Fluconazole	-	-	-	-	35	35

Bore size =6 mm.

Experimental

General methods :

Melting points are uncorrected. Optical rotations $[\alpha]_D$ were measured on a Equip-Tronics digital polarimeter model no. EQ 800 in CHCl_3 at 30 °C. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrum RXI (4000–450 cm^{-1}) FTIR spectrometer. ^1H NMR were obtained on a Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz FT NMR) NMR spectrometer for a sample in CDCl_3 solution with TMS as an internal reference. The mass spectra were recorded on a Micromass Quattro II triple quadruple mass spectrometer.

Aryl *S*-benzylisothiocarbamides (1a-g) :

The required aryl-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamides (1a-g) were prepared by the already known method¹⁶ which involves interaction of benzyl chloride with aryl thiocarbamides in ethanol, refluxed for 90 min followed by the basification of the resultant solution using dilute ammonium hydroxide to give the isothiocarbamides (1a-g).

Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -glucopyranosylisocyanate (2) :

Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -glucopyranosyl isocyanate (2) was prepared by interaction of tetra-*O*-acetyl- α -D-glucopyranosyl bromide and lead cyanate in anhydrous xylene medium¹⁷.

1-Aryl-5-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -glucopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2-isothiobiurets :

Condensation of phenyl-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamides (0.005 *M*, 1.2 g) and tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -glucopyranosyl isocyanate (0.005 *M*, 1.9 g), in benzene (20 mL) was carried out on boiling water bath for 4 h. The reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the

solvent was distilled off and the resultant sticky residue was triturated with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) to afford the solid with m.p. 100–101 °C. It was crystallized from water-alcohol.

1-Phenyl-5-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -glucopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2-isothiobiuret (3) :

IR (KBr) : ν 3356 (N-H), 3001 (Ar-H), 1745 (C=O), 1583 (C=N), 1382 (C-N), 1232 (C-O), 769 (C=S); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 7.43–6.43 (7H, m, N-H (Ar) and Ar-H), 6.2 (1H, d, NH (glu.)), 5.72–5.03 (7H, m, glucopyranosyl ring), 4.35–3.95 (5H, m, Ar- CH_2), 2.4–1.8 (12H, m, 4COCH₃); ESI Mass (*m/z*) : 615.4 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$), 331, 271, 169, 109 (Found : C, 56.70; H, 5.40; N, 6.75; S, 5.25. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{33}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{S}$: C, 56.58; H, 5.36; N, 6.82; S, 5.20%).

1-*o*-Cl-Phenyl-5-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -glucopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2-isothiobiuret (3b) :

IR (KBr) : ν 3346 (N-H), 3000 (Ar-H), 1746 (C=O), 1613 (C=N), 1382 (C-N), 766 (C=S); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 7.5–6.5 (10H, m, N-H (Ar) and Ar-H), 5.58 (1H, d, NH (glu.)), 5.21–4.7 (7H, m, glucopyranosyl ring), 4.35–4.01 (5H, m, Ar- CH_2), 2.1–1.8 (12H, m, 4COCH₃); ESI Mass (*m/z*) : 649 (not located) (M^+), 331, 271, 169, 109 (Found : C, 53.50; H, 4.80; N, 6.55; S, 4.99. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{SCl}$: C, 53.62; H, 4.93; N, 6.47; S, 4.93%).

1-*m*-Cl-Phenyl-5-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -glucopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2-isothiobiuret (3c) :

^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 7.5–6.5 (10H, m, N-H (Ar.) and Ar-H), 5.58 (1H, d, NH (glu.)), 5.21–4.7 (7H, m,

glucopyranosyl ring), 4.35–4.01 (5H, m, Ar-CH₂), 2.1–1.8 (12H, m, 4COCH₃) (Found : C, 53.50; H, 4.80; N, 6.55; S, 4.99. Calcd. for C₂₉H₃₂O₁₀N₃SCl : C, 53.62; H, 4.93; N, 6.47; S, 4.93%).

1-p-CI-Phenyl-5-tetra-O-acetyl-β-glucopyranosyl-2-S-benzyl-2-isothiobiuret (3d) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.5–6.5 (10H, m, N–H (Ar.) and Ar-H), 5.58 (1H, d, NH (glu.)), 5.21–4.7 (7H, m, glucopyranosyl ring), 4.35–4.01 (5H, m, Ar-CH₂), 2.1–1.8 (12H, m, 4COCH₃) (Found : C, 53.50; H, 4.80; N, 6.55; S, 4.99. Calcd. for C₂₉H₃₂O₁₀N₃SCl : C, 53.62; H, 4.93; N, 6.47; S, 4.93%).

1-o-Tolyl-5-tetra-O-acetyl-β-glucopyranosyl-2-S-benzyl-2-isothiobiuret (3e) :

IR (KBr) : ν 3459 (N–H), 2931 (Ar-H), 1750 (C=O), 1631 (C=N), 1379 (C–N), 674 (C=S); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.36–6.82 (10H, m, N–H (Ar.) and Ar-H), 5.53 (1H, d, NH (glu.)), 5.72–4.9 (7H, m, glucopyranosyl ring), 4.30–4.00 (5H, m, Ar-CH₂), 2.2 (3H, m, Ar-CH₃), 2.16–1.82 (12H, m, 4COCH₃); ESI Mass (*m/z*) : 630 (M⁺ + 1), 331, 271, 169, 109 (Found : C, 57.29; H, 5.45; N, 6.60; S, 5.15. Calcd. for C₃₀H₃₅O₁₀N₃S : C, 57.23; H, 5.56; N, 6.67; S, 5.08%).

1-m-Tolyl-5-tetra-O-acetyl-β-glucopyranosyl-2-S-benzyl-2-isothiobiuret (3f) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.36–6.82 (10H, m, N–H (Ar) and Ar-H), 5.53 (1H, d, NH (glu.)), 5.72 (7H, m, glucopyranosyl ring), 4.30–4.00 (5H, m, Ar-CH₂), 2.2 (3H, m, Ar-CH₃), 2.16–1.82 (12H, m, 4COCH₃) (Found : C, 57.29; H, 5.45; N, 6.60; S, 5.15. Calcd. for C₃₀H₃₅O₁₀N₃S : C, 57.23; H, 5.56; N, 6.67; S, 5.08%).

1-p-Tolyl-5-tetra-O-acetyl-β-glucopyranosyl-2-S-benzyl-2-isothiobiuret (3g) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.36–6.82 (10H, m, N–H (Ar.) and Ar-H), 5.53 (1H, d, NH (glu.)), 5.72–4.9 (7H, m, glucopyranosyl ring), 4.30–4.00 (5H, m, Ar-CH₂), 2.2 (3H, m, Ar-CH₃), 2.16–1.82 (12H, m, 4COCH₃) (Found : C, 57.29; H, 5.45; N, 6.60; S, 5.15. Calcd. for C₃₀H₃₅O₁₀N₃S : C, 57.23; H, 5.56; N, 6.67; S, 5.08%).

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to SAIF, CDRI, Lucknow for providing the spectral data. Authors also thanks to Dr. S. G. Bhadange, Principal, Shri Shivaji College, Akola for encouragement and providing necessary facilities.

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